

THE ROLE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL RELATIONSHIPS IN THE FAMILY IN THE FORMATION OF A CHILD'S PERSONALITY

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Abstract. *In this article, the role of psychological relations in the family in the formation of the child's personality and the serious attention paid by parents to the upbringing of children in families, and the issues aimed at bringing up a perfect person and a mentally healthy child. The focus is on parent-child relationships.*

Keywords: *family, child, upbringing, Keu test, attitude, perfect person, Uzbek families, psychological literacy.*

Community and state care for the family has become an important direction of our social policy. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoev, pays special attention to family issues. Shavkat Mirziyoev's speech in his Address to the Oliy Majlis specifically focused on the processes of preparing young people for family and forming their legal concepts and education: - "In a word, from the birth of a child to the age of 30 During this period, a comprehensive and continuous system will be created that will support him in every way, help him find a worthy place in life. The experience of the world shows that the investment spent on raising the young generation to adulthood in all respects will bring ten or a hundred times more benefits to the society.

"No matter how difficult it is, we must find unique and effective methods of youth education that are in tune with today. It is necessary to protect our dear children from destructive and harmful ideas, crime, drug addiction, indifference, moral poverty. All of us, first of all, dear young people, should be active in eliminating such negative situations. You are certainly capable of preserving the spiritual power and eternal traditions of our people and glorifying them to the whole world», said President Shavkat Mirziyoev in an open dialogue with young people at the forum.

It should be noted that the sacred concept of the family with its many problems has always excited the minds of researchers. For example, sociologists have been debating whether it is enough to have a husband and a wife to create a family, or whether it is necessary to have children for the union of a man and a woman to be called a family. From a legal point of view, it does not matter much. Lawyers, on another issue - that is, can the union of a husband and wife without observing the procedures and conditions stipulated by the law be considered a family? they argue in the sense of This is about a man and a woman openly living together for a long time without registering a legal marriage, even if they are living together and raising their children. Strictly speaking, such a union cannot be a marriage and does not create any legal consequences, excluding the rights and obligations of the parents towards the children. That is why a civil marriage or a marriage called a church (mosque) marriage cannot give birth to a family in the legal sense. It creates only maternal and paternal relations, i.e., blood kinship ties that give rise to a certain amount of rights (for example, the right of children to inherit the property of any of the parents).

The place of the family, which we consider to be a sacred place, consists of two pillars - husband and wife, and the one who firmly binds these two pillars to each other is the child. In the development of a child into a perfect person in all respects, the issue of education in parent-child relations is of great importance. Studying the relationship between parents and children in the environment of Uzbek families is thinking about the future of the nation and the state. In the effective course of parent-child relations in the family, it is necessary to pay attention to the issues of determining the nature of the attitude of parents to their children in Uzbek families. Education is not only a personal work of parents, but also a social duty. The correct use of the forms and methods of educational influences prepares the ground for raising healthy children in all aspects. In addition, parents are praised not for having given birth to a child, but for raising him to be a decent and moral adult.

Forming and educating young people on the basis of enlightenment, forming legal culture in them, improving legal education and training is one of the most urgent tasks of today. "The youth of today's world is the largest generation in the history of mankind in terms of numbers, ... if we take into account the fact that they make up 2 billion people, the future of our planet, the well-being of our planet depends on how these young people mature into human beings". In this regard, the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev proposed the development of a legal document on the development of multilateral international cooperation in social support of the young generation, protection of their rights and interests - the UN International Convention on the Rights of Youth. On September 20, 2017, he emphasized in his report at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly.

In the family, starting from the behavior of the parents and the adults in the family, speech culture, dressing, dealing with people, even the attitude to the environment and similar seemingly simple situations have a great impact on the upbringing of the child. How a child will develop into a person in the future depends more on his parents and his family and the environment in which he is formed. At present, attention has been paid to the education of young people as mature and well-rounded individuals. Raising young people to become morally clean, physically healthy and mature people is one of the most important requirements for the family. We used the Keu test "Interactions in the family, determination of parents' attitude to their children" to determine the characteristics of parent-child relationship observation in the family.

Level	Excellent	Middle	Bad
Fathers	53.0	45.0	2.0
Mothers	69.0	31.0	-

Table 1. Levels of parents' attitude towards their children (in %)

These results indicate the level of parents' relationship with their children, emotional relationships, spending more time with the child, taking care of him, talking with him about a topic, reading fairy tales and stories when he was young. 'indicates that it is done by more mothers. We can see above that asking the child to summarize the stories read or told has a good effect on the emotional and mental formation of the child.

Therefore, it can be seen that mothers have more of these characteristics of attitude at the "Very Good" level. The fact that fathers mainly fulfill their duties as breadwinners in the family leads to the low level of communication they establish with the child, and the low frequency of organizing conversations based on the child's interest. Therefore, it is clear that the father's attitude towards the child is more average. The fact that some fathers are involved in work, have a high

professional position, high social status, or indulge in negative vices, shows that their relationship with the child can be bad. We can once again witness that we should not forget the relationship with the father in the development of the child, the role of the father in the upbringing of the child. It is especially important for mothers to be educated and to acquire the necessary knowledge about child education.

So, the relationship of parents with children is very good, it is seen in moderate cases. In this case, it became clear that the scope of communication of mothers and the opportunities for regular implementation of this communication are available in the family environment. In the conditions of the Uzbek family, there are certain positive aspects of the relationship between parents and children, which in turn are reflected in the formation of the child's character. Based on the results of the conducted research, we consider it reasonable to make the following conclusions:

- As long as parents are able to show the characteristics of conformity to their roles, it was observed that they can show and show the characteristics of demandingness, sometimes tenderness and care.

- In the family, it was observed that mothers devote more time to their children than fathers.

- It has been shown that fathers are superior to mothers in terms of proper attitude and reasonable behavior towards the child and his behavior.

- Mothers create more opportunities for the child's development in various ways. It has been shown that mothers are more likely to monitor their children. It was found that fathers treat the child more often as an equal and understand him in a friendly manner.

- The conformity of current parents to their roles was reflected in their very good, average level of relationships with their children.

- It has been shown that children are not indifferent to the interactions and situations in the parents' family. This, in turn, shows the predominance of positive rather than negative tendencies in the characteristics of children's relationship with their parents' family. We believe that it is necessary to determine the specific psychological characteristics of the relationship between parents and children in the Uzbek family, and to make the following recommendations based on the conclusions and the results obtained:

- Constantly explaining to parents that they are directly responsible for their children's education and what kind of person they will be in the future after they have the responsibility and happiness of parenting;

- Parents have good human relations in front of their children, including promoting exemplary behavior;

- Organizing conversations about interpersonal relations with the participation of parents and children in the neighborhood;

- To pay attention to the issues of psychological literacy of parents in raising children, to organize local psychological counseling centers.

In conclusion, it can be said that the relationship between parents and children is one of the leading factors in the formation of a child's personality. All the changes and spiritual reforms carried out in our society are aimed at educating a well-rounded person in the society, which in turn is about educating a good citizen and a well-rounded member of society. We must not forget that the formation of a child as a mature person in society begins with the family. The importance of the role of parents in raising a child, especially the attitude of mothers towards the child, contributes a lot to the child's emotional development. If parents or other family members create

a healthy psychological environment for the child in the family, if the persons responsible for the child's upbringing acquire the knowledge and skills related to upbringing, mastering the modern methods of education and upbringing, the child's personal Good results will be achieved if the educational process is carried out based on individual qualities.

The important task of a mother in raising a child is to show kindness to her children, protect them from various harms, feed them on time, wash them, dress them cleanly, and not allow them to catch a cold. Every action of a mother in the family circle, every word that comes out of her mouth can have a positive or negative effect on her child's education and formation. Copying her every move, she takes a model of her mother's vocabulary for her unformed vocabulary. First of all, the peacefulness of the family and the kindness of the family members to each other occupy an important and worthy place in the upbringing of children. In the formation of a child's personality, it is not only the role of parents in the family, but also kindergarten educators and pedagogues of secondary schools should acquire knowledge related to child education. The nature and behavior of the child depends on the environment in the family. Of course, good children do not grow up on their own, but grow up in the family under the supervision of their parents. Therefore, if we prepare family members to properly organize psychological relations between parents and children in the family environment, we will prevent conflicts and conflict situations that may occur in our lives.

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